

Effect of Building Information Modelling On Construction Projects Risks Management in Kenya

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper was to establish the effect of Building Information Modelling (BIM) in the management of construction projects risks in Kenya. The study target population is 462 registered consulting architects and engineers in Nairobi City County where explanatory survey research was used. A simple and random sampling technique was to select the respondents for the study. The research data were collected by use of questionnaires and secondary data collected from journals and publications. The data were analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively using SPSS version 24. The study revealed that BIM design and visualization reduces the risk of making changes later in the project. Also, cost estimation and budgeting increase construction project's risk management. Moreover, BIM scheduling provides the project team a very powerful four-dimensional representation of the project which is effective in construction project risk management. Further, BIM multi-disciplinary collaboration & coordination makes it relatively simple to make a change to the building model thereby effectively managing construction project risk. There is, therefore, a need for contractors to utilize BIM for project design to have a more accurate and realistic design. As well, there is need for contractors to utilize BIM since it is a better cost estimation tool. Also, it is utmost necessary to use BIM to facilitate resource optimization and better tracking of project activities. Finally, contractors could also utilize BIM to mitigate the risk of double-counting of materials from different disciplines.

Keywords: *Building Information Modelling (BIM), cost estimation, BIM scheduling, construction projects risks*

Introduction

Whenever you undertake a project, there is always some element of risk, whether from cost overruns, project delays, or buildings not performing as expected. While adopting building information modelling (BIM) cannot eradicate all risks, it enables us to de-risk many areas across the project life cycle. This provides greater certainty and ensures that key project milestones are met, and assets delivered as expected (Pryke, 2016). The Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a highly discussed topic nowadays. In some parts of the world, BIM has become common, usually by means of some degree of standardization and government support (Tomek & Matejka, 2014).

Over the last three decades, Information technology (IT) has been used extensively in transforming the construction industry and has been deemed as a solution to save construction projects. In this view, Building Information Technology (BIM) has played a big role in revolutionising the way to design, document and procure buildings. BIM promises to become a new international benchmark for building design and documentation across industry on the basis of improved efficiencies and collaboration capabilities (Aranda-Mena, Crawford, Chevez, & Froese, 2009). With the growing use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) for vertical building projects, the use of BIM is increasing in infrastructure construction projects (Lee, Salama, & Wang, 2014).

BIM fulfils its purpose through all the stages of the project delivering benefits in terms of improved design quality, easiness to implement, information sharing ability, reduction of construction costs and design errors, faster work and shortening the construction time, enhancing energy efficiency and supporting construction and project management (Blanco & Chen, 2014). The construction industry is one of the world's largest industries, but it is also one of the most fractured (Lindblad, 2013).

As stated by a BIM utilization survey, BIM is used in the design phase (55%), the detail design and tender stage (52%), construction stage (35%), feasibility stage (27%), and operation and maintenance stage (9%) (Eadie, Browne, Odeyinka, McKeown, & McNiff, 2013). This shows that the uptake of BIM in the construction industry is being implemented at different rates within the different phases of construction – the lowest being operation and construction, while the highest in the design phase.

In recent years, the awareness and concerns about risks have risen in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry with possibility of occurrence of hazards gradually rising because of increase of structural complexity, growing project size and new and complex construction methods (Zou, Kiviniemi, & Jones, 2015). BIM has been used in commercial building construction in recent years to virtually construct a facility prior to its actual physical construction, in order to reduce uncertainty, improve safety, work out problems, and to simulate and analyse potential impacts (Lee, Salama, & Wang, 2014).

According to the Kenya's Vision 2030, the infrastructure sector has been identified as one of the foundations of socio-economic transformation, while housing and urbanization have been identified as one of the key social sectors of the social pillar (Kenya Vision 2030, 2007). With this, it is evident that Kenya will be facing increased developments in the construction industry, i.e. both infrastructure and housing sectors, thus increasing the need for more innovative and cost-effective systems in the industry. As a result, AEC practitioners are constantly on the move to adopt new technology that will ensure reduced construction costs for maximum returns and maintaining project quality (Kagai, 2017).

The 3D Building Information Modelling techniques are slowly gaining traction, but there is a need for a lot more education and awareness within the East African construction industry before BIM takes a solid foothold (TheBIG5ConstructEastAfrica, 2018). BIM in Kenya is still very much associated with software and especially with Autodesk's Revit and Graphisoft's ArchiCAD. Currently, no institution is offering BIM courses or even training that includes BIM as a topic and thus, it is very unlikely that the BIM agenda will be set by the government in Kenya. It will have to be guided by the industry and private developers - especially those companies that come from regions where BIM is gradually becoming a way of life (Waigwa, 2016). However, one of the major challenges facing development projects in Kenya is corruption and ICT is also viewed as an effective tool in fighting rampant corruption in the construction industry through fraud detection, improved transparency through coordination and facilitating information sharing (Ndemo, 2015). With the increasing uptake of the BIM technology, there is also potential for BIM consultants that will be needed to offer training and hand-holding to firms that are willing to start changing their ways as well as offer BIM modelling services for energy analysis and sun path analysis, MEP and structural modelling for clash detection and cost analysis (Waigwa, 2016).

In Nairobi County, there exists no formal organization towards the implementation of BIM. The anticipated audience for BIM is, therefore, disintegrated and lacking a united focus. This situation results in a lack of capacity regarding numbers agitating for and working towards BIM adoption. The best-placed institutions to champion BIM adoption in Nairobi are the County Government, professional organizations, and educational institutions by offering support financially and in capacity building by training and in research (Gitee & Muchelule, 2018).

Contractors are harnessing 4D (time) technologies linking their construction programmes to the design team's BIM model, thus enabling varying construction strategies to be rehearsed, hence reducing site risk and optimising delivery. Cost risk is also being managed by allowing commercial teams to more effectively link into the design model using 5D techniques that link into predefined templates that feed into historical cost databases (Sinclair, 2018). There has long been compelling evidence that many safety risks are created in the early design stage of projects. Hence, it can be argued that one of the most effective means of dealing with a hazard is to eliminate it at source, that is, Prevention through Design (PtD). Studies have confirmed that the utilization of Building Information Modelling (BIM) enhanced the optimization of the design to yield the best outcome at the design stage which led to better risk management. Nonetheless, the potential of BIM for PtD is

yet to be explored (Kamardeen, 2010). PtD leveraging on BIM consists of three tasks: 1. Hazard profiling of BIM model elements, 2. providing safe design suggestions for revising high hazard profiled elements, and 3 and proposing on-site risk controls for hazards that are uncontrollable through design revisions (Jabri, 2015).

Problem formulation

According to the Deloitte Construction 2017 Report, it shows that 48% of projects were over budget and 87% of projects had time overruns – meaning that only 13% of projects were completed on time. It also showed that where projects were contracted irregularly, procurement challenges became a major factor leading to project delays and cost overruns (Deloitte, 2017). Structural defects are frequently identified too late, often after a catastrophic collapse. In 2009 Kenyan officials estimated that 65% of Kenya's buildings fail to meet code standards. Between 2006 and 2014, seventeen buildings spontaneously collapsed in Kenya alone and caused eighty-four deaths and more than 290 injuries (Fernandez, 2014).

In February 2018, the Kenya National Assembly's Public Investment's Committee summoned the Kenya National Highway Authority (KENHA) management to answer questions on the slow pace of road projects worth more than 50 Billion Kenya Shillings, which resulted to the agency paying contractors millions of shillings in interest (Mwere, 2018). The takeover in technology has been identified as one of the top four factors driving the growth of Africa's construction industry (Kiganda, 2017). This technology – mostly in BIM – has led to the increased adoption of the technology in an attempt to reduce time and cost overruns – as well as other project-related risks. The frequent cases of collapse of buildings in Kenya have become a major concern among all the stakeholders in the local construction industry.

In a bid to stem the unfortunate occurrences, President Uhuru Kenyatta, in January 2015 commissioned an audit of all the buildings in Nairobi and it was found that only 42% of the structures in the city were found fit for habitation (Thuita, 2017). Poor project design is another driver of cost overrun – with construction often starting based on incomplete designs. This sees building contractors subsequently requesting more information and later additions to the project, resulting in both cost overruns and delays. This can be avoided through detailed design review for completeness and conformance to the owner's scope as well as interdisciplinary coordination prior to construction. Even in the event a design flaw arises once construction has started, fluid communication across the team of designers, project managers and contractors can minimize cost overruns (Soko, 2015).

Planning is a basic part of contracting and the construction process. In the projects that implement BIM, visualizations can be made from previously produced models, in contrast to the traditional projects, in which the building visualization had to be made from the very start (Mering, et al., 2017). Several studies have been done on the management of risks in Kenyan construction projects. Gichunge (2000) did research on risk management in the building industry in Kenya, an analysis of time and cost risks. Talukhaba (1999) did an investigation into factors causing construction project delays in Kenya.

Kimemia (2015) did a study on the determinants of project delays in the construction industry in Kenya, the case of selected road projects implemented by Kenya National Highways Authority in Kenya's Coast region. Musyoka (2012) researched project risk management practices and the success of capital projects in Kenya. However, none of the studies has dealt with the management of the construction projects risks by utilizing the BIM technology – which presents a knowledge gap. With the available knowledge on the capabilities of BIM technology, it is evident that it can be utilized in construction projects to identify, measure, mitigate and control project risks. This study, therefore, sought to fulfill the gap by investigating and relating the contribution of the BIM technology in managing risks in construction projects in Nairobi City County, Kenya.

Theoretical Review

Technology acceptance model (TAM) is an information systems theory that models how users come to accept and use technology (Wikipedia). It was formulated by Richard Bagozzi, Fred Davis and Paul Warshaw in the 1980s. It explains the factors that influence the decision about how and when users will use a new technology – which include: 1) Perceived Usefulness (PU) which was defined by Fred Davis as “the degree to which a person

believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance; 2) Perceived ease-of-use (PEOU) which was defined by Davis as “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort (Davis, 1989).

Bagozzi, Davis and Warshaw stated that “Because new technologies such as personal computers are complex, and an element of uncertainty exists in the minds of decision-makers with respect to the successful adoption of them, people from attitudes and intentions toward trying to learn to use the new technology prior to initiating efforts directed at using. Attitudes towards usage and intentions to use may be ill-formed or lacking in conviction, or else may occur only after preliminary strivings to learn to use the technology evolve. Thus, actual usage may not be a direct or immediate consequence of such attitudes and intentions” (Bagozzi, Davis, & Warshaw, 1992).

FIGURE 2-1: The Technology Acceptance Model.

Olumide Durodolu in his publication on Technology Acceptance Model as a predictor of using information systems to acquire information literacy skills asserted that external variables which are factors outside an individual such as training, experience and system quality affects the two factors PU and PEOU which influence the users’ attitude towards the use of a given technology and its ultimate use (Durodolu, 2016). The main external factors that are usually manifested are social factors, cultural factors and political factors. Social factors include language, skills and facilitating conditions.

Political factors are mainly the impact of using technology in politics and political crisis. The attitude to use is concerned with the user’s evaluation of the desirability of employing a particular information system application. Behavioural intention is the measure of the likelihood of a person employing the application (Surendran, 2012). Dr. Mohamed Al Haderi noted that other information quality affects user’s intention to adopt the technology especially after its usefulness has been established and also established a positive effect that government and top management support has on the intentional behaviour throughout the positive effect on perceived usefulness and ease of use (Al-Haderi, 2014).

Institutional factors refer to the aspects within the organization related to work and the instrument to facilitate the accomplishment of the work. For example, organizational support and rewards influence workers’ beliefs in using technology to accomplish the work (Lewis, Agarwal, & Sambamurthy, 2003). However, some researchers have critiqued the model with the argument that the model does not address how other variables affect the core variables of TAM such as usefulness and ease of use. It also paid insufficient attention to understanding other factors such as system outputs and the system itself – which impact the major variables in TAM (Abugabah, Sanzogni, & Poropat, 2009).

In this study, TAM will be applied to the BIM design process, which involves activities whose usefulness and ease of use are evident for both the professional designers and, most importantly, the client/major shareholders. With the generation of the BIM model and the BIM visualization, it will be more useful for the client since understanding of the design will be easier and faster. This will also hasten the decision-making process since the

client will be better informed of the design construct. The limitation of this theory will be its lack of application to custom organizational systems and, thus, difficult to identify the relationship between different discipline-based project teams working on the same project.

Review of Literature

Building Information Modelling on Project Design

Documentation has been a necessary component of project work throughout history. However, there has been a paradigm shift in how people communicate through documentation, from paper to electronic forms. Product development and manufacturing have long relied on drawings to communicate, and as those drawings have migrated from paper to CAD, the effect on the development and manufacturing processes has been profound (Lee C. , 2008). As the architect or engineer (A/E) completes a new design for a construction project, it is handed over to someone who will have to build it. The A/E has attempted to put every detail regarding that project on the two-dimensional drawings, any additional renderings, and other construction documents. Inevitably, some items are omitted, or other errors are made. In fact, the quality of these construction documents has been cited as a significant issue in the construction industry (Larrick, 2007).

At this point, what traditionally happens is the construction personnel discover the errors or issues and they will have to reconcile them with the A/E. This can be an iterative and time-consuming process as the design is further developed and defined. Other reasons for changing the design exist as well, such as the owner making changes to the project. These changes are often due to the owner's need to physically see the project before deciding on some of the details. In any case, the risk to the project's cost and schedule at this point in the process is based on these changes not being discovered until after construction has begun. At that point, changes are a direct risk to the cost and timing of the project. These types of issues in the design phase can be minimized when modelling in the BIM environment, as BIM offers some very distinct advantages (Lee C. , 2008).

As a building design is developed with BIM, or modelled, the construction personnel can be brought in as part of the process at a much earlier point in the project. Instead of waiting for the A/E to complete the design first, the contractor can begin to identify constructability issues in the building model on a real-time basis rather than an iterative "hand-off" process (Deitrick, 2007) that can waste a significant amount of time. This real-time development of the building model can save time and money later in the project lifecycle. In response to the issue of owners making late changes, based on physical sight, most BIM tools offer a very high level of visualization features. The ability to see the building in three dimensions, not only from the exterior, but to actually "walk through" the building model early in the design stage helps ensure owners are seeing what they want and are satisfied with the design.

The owner no longer has to wait until construction has begun to "see" what it looks like (Lee C. , 2008). The risk of making changes later in the project is again minimized through this ability to visualize the project early in the design process. When the building model is completed with this amount of collaborative effort between the A/E, the owner, and the contractor, the result is a more robust design with minimal risk of changes at the time of construction (Deitrick, 2007). Findings from a research study conducted by Jun, Xiangyu, Wenchi and Bo (2014) revealed that BIM is useful in enhancing efficiency through visualization of the architectural design model and communication among the relevant stakeholders.

This was in comparison with the traditional practice where designers use 2D CAD to create design models. Hence the process ends up wasting a lot of time and thus daunting (Wang, Wang, Shou, & Xu, 2014). Another way to demonstrate the advantages of working in the BIM environment is to consider the lessons learned or the project review process. Throughout any project cycle, there are a number of "lessons learned." Good project management skills would dictate that these lessons learned be disseminated throughout the organization and applied to future projects for their benefit.

However, many lessons learned are specific to the particular project, and therefore do not necessarily apply to the next projects. But when operating within a BIM environment on a project, most lessons are learned from the virtual construction process before any ground is broken. Instead of struggling through real issues with cost and timing implications, the issues are discovered in the virtual project where they can be addressed with an optimized cost and timing solution. When the physical construction does begin, it is as if it were the second time going through the project, but with the benefit of already having the lessons learned (Ivanikiw, 2007).

Building Information Modelling Cost Estimation

A cost estimate can be viewed as the task of determining the quantities of work to be performed, with the production rate and cost of the resources required to perform that work (Al-Mashta, 2010). Cost estimating internal process steps do not have a commonly adapted structure. Consequently, experts and researchers do not adhere to exact specific steps during the cost estimating process. The preparation of cost estimate depends mainly on developing a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) that breaks down the project into subsets of items or packages (Elbeltagi, Hosny, Dawood, & Elhakeem, 2014).

Assuming a standard set of construction documents, one of the next steps under a traditional construction project would be for the construction manager to prepare a detailed estimate. Putting together a reliable estimate has usually involved a person with the skills and experience in pulling together reasonably accurate estimates in a reasonable time. It is not cost effective to count every brick, bolt, or beam in the building, so estimators with the skills to balance these aspects of the estimating task are valued in the construction industry. However, in the BIM environment, estimating is a simpler, easier, and more accurate exercise (Deitrick, 2007).

Working in the BIM environment allows not only the collaboration between the A/E and contractor but preserves all the information that went into the building model as it gets transferred to subsequent parts of the construction process (Lee C. , 2008). Traditionally, cost estimation for building projects starts with quantification (Sabol, 2008). Quantification is a time-consuming task; it consumes from 50% to 80% of the cost estimator's time on a project (Autodesk 2007). In order to develop quantity take-offs, estimators typically begin by digitizing the drawings or doing manual take-offs. All these methods introduce the potential for human error and propagate any inaccuracies there may be in the original drawings. By using a Building Information Model instead of drawings, the take-offs, counts, and measurements can be generated directly from the underlying model. Therefore, the information is always consistent with the design. And, when a change is made in the design, it will automatically ripple to all related construction documentation and schedules, as well as all the take-offs, counts, and measurements that are used by the estimator.

Preparing of BIM model, based on the WBS that is previously developed, can reduce the time needed to achieve a high-quality building by improving design and construction integration and quantity take-off accuracy. Therefore, it is most beneficial to convert the design into BIM software to allow extracting more detailed spatial and material quantities directly from the building model in a timely manner (Elbeltagi, Hosny, Dawood, & Elhakeem, 2014). As demonstrated by Neil Calvert, BIM 5D modelling relates to the estimating and cost aspects of a building. Each element within the building model has a cost associated with it. This allows for a detailed analysis to be done regarding budgets. It also allows the delivery team to make accurate predictions regarding how much needs to be done at any given time in order to meet the construction targets (Calvert, 2013).

Research Gaps

From the literature reviewed, it is evident that numerous research studies have been carried out on the BIM technology, but very few have addressed the relationship between the BIM technology and the management of risks in construction projects. Additionally, most of the studies have been done in the developed countries where the BIM agenda is being driven by the governments seeking standardization of the same. As noted by Wambia Waigwa, it is very unlikely that the BIM agenda in Kenya will be set by the government. Instead, it will be guided by the industry and the private developers and especially those companies that are from regions

where BIM is gradually becoming a way of life (Waigwa, 2016). In this regard, this research study aims at addressing the gap and establishing the effect of BIM technology in managing risks in construction projects in Kenya – specifically in the capital Nairobi City.

Gitee and Muchelule addressed the effect of BIM on project implementation in Nairobi county. The study focused on how project design, project estimations, project scheduling and project information asymmetry influenced the implementation and performance of projects (Gitee & Muchelule, 2018). Pauline Maina (2018) noted that a considerable number of her study respondents felt that BIM is less efficient in schedule and cost estimation and monitoring, material scheduling and project risk management, despite literature cited supporting its efficiency. This indicated an aspect of BIM that was not well actualized in Kenya thus recommended more studies to shed more light on how benefits can be derived from these BIM capabilities to avail more information to construction professionals (Maina, 2018). Marylyn Musyimi (2016) also researched on the adoption of BIM in construction project management in Kenya – with a case study of Nairobi county – where she researched on the BIM adoption level while focusing on the challenges facing the adoption of BIM technology and the strategies that aid the adoption of BIM (Musyimi, 2016). These studies, however, did not cover the influence that BIM has on the management of project risks in the construction industry. In some cases, the researchers recommended this as an area of further study. This presents a research gap to be filled in this study.

Methodology

The research design adopted was explanatory survey research. The target population of the study, therefore, encompasses 462 professional consultants in the construction industry. The sampling frame for this study was the list of all the 195 registered consulting architects and 381 registered consulting engineers in Kenya. Sample size of study was obtained using Krejcie & Morgan, 1970 formula for finite population. Therefore, sample size was 210. As a result, a sample population of 80 architects and 130 engineers were selected, giving a total sample of 210 as shown in table 3.2 below. Simple random sampling was then used to determine the respondent from whom information was collected. This gave each member in the sample an equal and known probability of participating in the study (Lance & Hattori, 2016). Primary data was collected using questionnaires from the 210 respondents. The research data was collected by use of questionnaires. Data reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which is a measure of internal consistency, which shows how closely related a set of items are as a group and it is considered as a measure of scale reliability. For all quantitative data analysis, studies used multiple linear regression models to test the relationship between variables. R^2 was used to establish the goodness of fit of the estimated model (Oso & Onen, 2011). The overall statistical model used for analysis was in the form of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) model as shown below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Where

Y	=	represents the dependent variable (management of project risks)
β_0	=	represents the constant
$\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$	=	represents the coefficient of the independent variables
X_1	=	represents project design
X_2	=	represents project cost estimation
ε	=	represents the error term

Findings and Discussion

Out of the two hundred and ten respondents who were sampled and the questionnaires were administered, one hundred and thirty-six respondents responded. This gave a response rate of 64.7% percent. This response rate was satisfactory and followed Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) specification that a response rate of 50% is adequate for analysis and a response rate of 60% is good and a response rate of 70% and over is excellent. The study variables had alpha coefficients higher than 0.7. This meant that the collected data were reliable as they

had a relatively high internal consistency and could be generalized to reflect opinions of all respondents in the target population. The Cronbach alpha test showed values ranging from as low as 0.705 to as high as 0.911. These findings were in line with the benchmark suggested by Hair *et al.* (2010), who regard a coefficient of 0.60 to have an average reliability while a coefficient of 0.70 and above indicates that the instrument has a high reliability standard. Although most researchers generally consider an alpha value of 0.70 as the acceptable level of reliability coefficient, lower coefficient is also acceptable (Nunnally, 1978; Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). Therefore, it can be concluded that data collected from the pilot study were reliable and obtained the acceptable level of internal consistency. Therefore, all items were included in the survey instrument.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Statistics

BIM Design and Visualization

The study enquired from the respondent on BIM design and visualization. The respondents were required to give their view on a 5-point Likert scale that is strongly agreed, agree, neutral, disagreed and strongly disagreed. The results are illustrated in table 4.4 as shown below. The results on BIM Design and Visualization summed up to a mean of 3.44 and standard deviation of 0.490 implying that gaps exist regarding BIM Design and Visualization especially with reference to whether BIM makes it easy to sample different design options and identify the pros and cons, projects designed in BIM have better visualization which helps to capture client requirements better. The findings are in line with that of Lee, (2008) which established that BIM design and visualization reduces the direct risk to the cost and timing of the project. Similarly, Deitrick (2007) posited that BIM design and visualization enables contractors to identify constructability issues in the building model on a real-time basis rather an iterative process. To further corroborate the findings, Jun, Xiangyu, Wenchi and Bo (2014) revealed that BIM is useful in enhancing efficiency through visualization of architectural design model and communication among the relevant stakeholders. The results are also in tally with that of Ivanikiw (2007), which concluded that BIM makes it possible to identify issues in the virtual project whereby they can be addressed thereby making the physical construction seamlessly easy and sort of a second time doing the project. Finally, 74.3% of the respondents strongly disagreed that cost estimates from BIM are easy to interpret and understand thus enabling faster decision making. The results conform with the aggregate mean of 1.26 and a standard deviation of 0.44. Overall, the findings on Cost Estimation and Budgeting had a mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.60. The results suggest that most of the respondents agreed that Cost Estimation and Budgeting are present in the firm. Consistent with the results, Al-Mashta (2010) noted that cost estimate is of essence since it aids in determining the amount of work to be done, production rate and cost of resources. Consequently, the construction project risk is reduced. Similarly, (Deitrick (2007) elucidated that in the BIM environment, estimating is a simpler, easier, and more accurate exercise. The results are also in line with that of Calvert, (2013), which established that BIM allows the delivery team to make accurate predictions regarding how much needs to be done at any given time in order to meet the construction targets. Gitee & Muchelule (2018) further posited that the use of BIM project estimation significantly influences project implementation. Finally, 24.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that the use of BIM helps in faster capturing of client requirements, thus leading to better client satisfaction, 39% agreed, 3.7% disagreed though 39% were undecided. The item revealed a mean of 3.84 and a standard deviation of 0.84. Construction Project's Risks Management summed up to a mean of 3.69 and a standard deviation of 0.66.

The findings revealed that Design and Visualization were positively and significantly correlated with construction project's risks management ($r = 0.521$ $\rho < 0.01$). Further, Cost Estimation and Budgeting was positively and significantly correlated with construction project's risks management ($r = 0.412$, $\rho < 0.01$). These findings imply that Design and Visualization, Cost Estimation and Budgeting, are expected to influence construction project's risk management.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Construction project's risks management	BIM Design And Visualization	BIM cost estimation and budgeting
Construction project's risks management	3.69	0.66	1		
BIM Design And Visualization	3.44	0.49	.521**	1	
BIM cost estimation and budgeting	3.71	0.6	.412**	.397**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Regression analysis

Table 1 illustrates the model summary of the multiple regression model. The results in table 4.10 showed that all the four predictors (Design and Visualization, Cost Estimation and Budgeting) explained 52.6 percent variation of construction project's risks management ($R^2=0.526$). From the results, the above-discussed coefficient of determination was significant, as evidenced in F ratio of 36.283 with p value $0.000 < 0.05$ (level of significance). Therefore, the model was fit to predict construction project's risks management using Design and Visualization, Cost Estimation and Budgeting.

Research findings from Table 2 showed that Design and Visualization had coefficients of the estimate which was significant, basing on $\beta_1 = 0.327$ (p-value = 0.009 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$). Therefore, an increase in Design and Visualization by one-unit results in an increase in the construction project's risks management by 0.327 units. Furthermore, the effect of Design and Visualization was reiterated by the t-test value = 4.633, which implied that the standard error associated with the parameter is more than the effect of the parameter.

From Table 2, Cost Estimation and Budgeting had coefficients that was significant, basing on $\beta_2 = 0.251$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$). Therefore, for each unit increase in Cost Estimation and Budgeting, there is up to 0.251-units increase in construction project's risk management. Moreover, the effect of Cost Estimation and Budgeting was tested by the t-test value of 3.915 which implied that the effect of Cost Estimation and Budgeting surpasses that of the error.

Table 2 Regression Results

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	-1.35	0.51		-2.66	0.01
Design and Visualization	0.44	0.10	0.33	4.63	0.00
Cost Estimation and Budgeting	0.28	0.07	0.25	3.92	0.00
summary statistics					
R	0.73				
R Square	0.53				
Adjusted R Square	0.51				
F	36.28				
Sig.	0.00				

a Dependent Variable: construction project's risks management

Conclusion

BIM Design and Visualization had a positive and significant effect on the construction project's risk management. BIM design and visualization are of essence since it enables contractors to identify if there are any laden issues. If so, such issues are minimized at the design phase. As such, BIM is useful in enhancing

efficiency through visualization of architectural design model and communication among the key stakeholders. The take away is that with BIM design and visualization reduces the risk of making changes later in the project.

Further, cost estimation and budgeting increase construction project's risk management. Through cost estimation and budgeting it becomes easier to know prior the cost of resources, the amount of work to be done and the production rate. The implication is that with BIM there are better estimation tools that are accurate, reliable and dependable. Though it might be a daunting task to interpret the cost estimates, they cannot be compared to traditional methods since they are more convenient and they take relatively short time.

Recommendations

BIM design and visualization are instrumental in countering construction project's risks. It is therefore recommended for contractors to utilize BIM for project design to have a more accurate and realistic design. Besides that, the possibility of making errors is reduced at the design phase. Further, contractors need to ensure that clients are privy to the fact that the BIM software has better visualization to better capture client requirements as opposed to traditional design methods.

BIM is an invaluable resource when it comes to cost estimation and budgeting. Therefore, to improve construction projects risk management, there is a need for contractors to utilize BIM since it is a better cost estimation tool. BIM is also a great utility since it generates more accurate cost estimations. Besides, there is need to acquaint the relevant stakeholders on the manner in which to interpret and understand BIM when it comes to cost estimation and budgeting.

In connection with the results known above, this study makes a number of possible implications on the effects of Building Information Modelling on construction projects risk management in Nairobi City County, Kenya. First, this study has opened an insight into the factors influencing construction projects risks management in Nairobi County, Kenya thus expanding on previous literature that has focused mainly on developed countries. It has opened up further research avenues to compare and contrast these results with construction projects in other countries.

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